

FEATURES OF EASY QUIZ

Turdaliyev Sodiqjon Mo'minjonovich

Faculty of physics and mathematics faculty of the Department of mathematics and informatics of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Email: tsm080185@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10361816>

Abstract: In this article, given some information about Easy Quiz program and creating tests for 11classes of schools on the subject of Information Technology by using Easy Quiz.

Key words: test, quiz, matching, program, web-page.

Easy Quiz – is a common and easy computer program for creating tests, editing and testing knowledge. Using this program tests may ease the daily works of teacher and speed up checking the results, it means that it will done by chosen assessment system automatically.

In order to work with Easy Quiz program push the Easy Quiz editor. Easy Quiz provide with only and consistent interface in order to form tests. Choose the creating test from test information label. Write the name of test and direction also show the author of test.

Then, pass the question section. It should not be difficult while adding and choosing variation of questions and answers.

You may put photos , formulas and a special symbols to the text of question variation.

After making the list of questions , test parameters consists of: question number and order, assessment system, time limits and the report of final format.

t/r	Theme
1	Graphic objects and their describing types
2	Two and three dimension graphic types of computer
3	Working with the bases of Photoshop program. Photo Shop interface
4	Photo Shop toolbar and polyters
5	Work with graphic objects on Photoshop
6	To separate a piece of image as geometric figure on Photo shop
7	Another ways of separating image
8	Frame the images and change the shape in them
9	Layers in Photo shop and their usage
10	Color system in Photo shop
11	To work with colors in Photo shop
12	About channels and filters
13	To work with a brush and pencil
14	Placing geometric shapes and vector objects on the image
15	Placing text on the image
16	Web-page, web-site and web-design concepts
17	Web-design and its software. Create and decorate a web-page using macromedia flash software
18	Placing and decorating pictorial information on web-page
19	Create and decorate forms on web-pages
20	Placing animations on pages
21	Practical training
22	Audio date and working with them
23	Options for establishing links between web-pages
24	Information security concepts and efficiency indicators

25	The problems of information security. Components and methods of information protection
26	Regional and global computer network and its protection
27	Security issues of information sources stored on the internet
28	Electronic government
29	e-mail service structure
30	Computer viruses and virus protection methods

After doing parameters, you may save your tests by choosing place from file menu by **сохранит как** section.

While creating test on this program you may use these question types;

- Counter choice
- To choose a correct answer
- To choose a few correct answer
- To put in order
- Matching
- Free answer

You can create test on this program on the following languages:

- English;
- Bulgarian;
- French;
- German;
- Kazak;
- Poland;
- Russian;

- Ukrainian.

The language of test interface should be proper to the language of Easy Quiz while saving. For this choose Vid menu from program interface and language from language interface.

At schools the subject “Information Technology” is planned to 68 hours for 11 grade pupils, it consists of these order of themes.

Consider creating a test on the following topic using the Easy Quiz program. Topic: Web-page, web-site and web-design concepts.

We fill in the introductory part of the program as follows. After that go to the next paragraph and post question on the topic. We choose **Выбор одного правильного ответа** paragraph and enter the question.

It should be like this. We mark the correct answer item of the questions. Push the **Добавить вопрос** paragraph to add next questions. Enter 10 tests and save it on the topic.

Choose Файл →сохранение теста paragraph for saving. We save the test by specifying the desired location. Paragraph 3 of the program is the related to setting up the test.

References:

1. Eassyquizzy.com.site
2. Ziyonet social network.
3. The book “Information technology”of 11 class.
4. S.M.Turdaliyev, A.R.Yuldoshev, IIDjo' rayev, T.V.Mamadaliyev. Axborot xavfsizligini biznes uchun strategic qilish. ACADEMICIA: Xalqaro ko'p tarmoqli tadqiqot jurnali. 2021/4/4.
5. Xilolaxon Ergasheva. FUNKSIYALARNI TEKSHIRISH VA ULARNING GRAFIKLARINI YASASH ALGORITMLARI VA DASTURIY VOSITALARI. Interpretation and researches. 2023/5/27.
6. Turdaliyev Sodiqjon Muminjonovich. Galaxy xalqaro fanlararo tadqiqot jurnali. 2023/6/17. Kompyuter o'yining o'smir shaxsiga ijobiy va salbiy ta'siri.
7. Ilyosovich, DI (2022). MOBIL ILOVALAR ORQALI O'ZI-O'ZINI TA'LIM. XALQARO TADQIQAT, IT, MUHENDISLIK VA IJTIMOY FANLAR JURNALI ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876 , 16 (5), 109-113.
8. Iloyovich, D. I. (2022). INFORMATION SECURITY AND CYBERSECURITY TRAINING IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM. Open Access Repository, 9(12), 14-16.
9. Hakimova, YT (2023). MASOFIY TA'LIM JARAYONIDA BULUT TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH “INFORMATIKA METODIKASI” FANINI O'QITISH METODIKASI. Ochiq kirish ombori , 9 (6), 238-240.
10. Hakimova, Y. T. (2022). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MASOFAVIY TA'LIMNI JORIY QILISH BOSQICHLAR. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(6), 1139-1142.
11. Hakimova, Y. T. (2023). MASOFAVIY TA'LIM JARAYONIDA INFOGRAFIKADAN FOYDALANISH VA UNING AFZAL TOMONLARI. Conferencea, 116-119
12. Iloyovich, D. I. (2022). INFORMATION SECURITY AND CYBERSECURITY TRAINING IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM. Open Access Repository, 9(12), 14-16.
13. Iloyovich, D. I. (2022). Training on Safe Use of Information and Cybersecurity in the Higher Education System. Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology, 15, 62-64.

14. Turdaliyev, SM, Yuldashev, AR, Djo'rayev, II, & Mamadaliyev, TV (2021). Axborot xavfsizligini biznes uchun strategik qilish. ACADEMICIA: Xalqaro multidisipliner tadqiqot jurnali , 11 (4), 1019-1021.
15. Iloyovich, DI (2022). Oliy ta'lim tizimida axborotdan xavfsiz foydalanish va kiberxavfsizlik bo'yicha trening. Texas muhandislik va texnologiya jurnali , 15 , 62-64.

